

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Challenges of parents and their child's academic performance in modular distance learning

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Abstract

The study focuses on the challenges of parents and their child's academic performance in science in modular distance learning. In this descriptive-survey research design, data were gathered from 10 parents of grade four pupils in San Nicolas Elementary School using convenience sampling. Gathered data were systematically treated and analyzed using frequency, percentage count, mean, standard deviation, and Pearson-r correlation. Findings revealed that individual-related challenges such as supervision of child's studies, and poor teaching skills were the most significant challenges parents experienced in implementing modular learning. Parents disagreed that instructional and institutional challenges affect them in modular distance learning. The respondents' children performed satisfactorily in science during the first and second quarters of the school year. There was a moderately significant relationship between individual-related and instructional-related challenges. However, a weak significant relationship is surfaced between parents' institutional-related challenges and their child's academic performance. No significant difference was observed regarding individual-related, instructional-related, and institutional-related challenges when grouped according to their profile variables. The researcher concluded that this study on modular distance learning contributed fairly and minimally to students' science performance brought about by continued social and academic adjustment. School and parents' involvement in implementing modular learning is essential for improving the modality.

Keywords: Challenges; Individual-related; Instructional-related; Institutional-related; Academic performance; Modular learning

1. Introduction

Many educational institutions in the Philippines planned strategies in using modular distance learning and e-learning. This study aimed to investigate parents' challenges and their child's academic performance. It sought to answer the following questions: (1) What challenges do parents have regarding the modular distance learning in terms of individual-related, instructional-related, and institutional-related; (2) What is the level of academic performance of grade 4 pupils in science; (3) Is there a significant relationship between the challenges met by parents and the academic performance of the students?

In the research made by Montoya (2020), she elaborated on the importance of the role of parents being the first teacher and the home as the first place where learning takes place. It is revealed by Trovela (2021) that challenges such as time management, limited knowledge of the parents on the topics in the modules, and independence in learning are the common challenges parents face in implementing modular distance learning.

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2. Methods

The respondents of this study were the parents of the grade four pupils, using the convenience sampling technique. This study used a descriptive-survey research design to investigate parents' challenges on the implementation of modular distance learning and the relationship of these challenges to the academic performance of their child. The researcher utilized a 4-point Likert scale. The questionnaire consists of three parts: Part A- parents' challenges in the implementation of modular distance learning as to individual-related challenges, instructional-related challenges, and institutional-related challenges; and Part B-student's academic performance for the first and second quarters of the school year. Data gathered were systematically treated and analyzed using descriptive and inferential statistics to achieve a correct and reliable result. Mean and standard deviation was utilized to determine how the parents' challenges affect their child's performance. Pearson r-correlation was used to determine the significant relationship between the challenges met by the parents and the students' academic performance.

3. Results

Here are the findings and results of the study.

Table 1 Individual-related Challenges Perceived by Parents

Individual-Related Challenges	Mean SD	Interpretation
I lack sufficient time to supervise.	2.50 ± 0.87	Agree
Difficulty in handling child misbehaviour.	2.54 ± 0.95	Agree
I lack experience and/or training with instructional technologies.	2.80 ± 0.91	Agree
I lack background knowledge on the subject.	2.69 ± 0.89	Agree
I have poor teaching skills.	2.83 ± 0.80	Agree

Table 2 Instructional-related Challenges Perceived by Parents

Instructional-Related Challenges	Mean SD	Interpretation
Distributed printed materials are incomplete and not in order.	2.29 ± 0.93	Disagree
Science material contents are too lengthy.	2.53 ± 0.86	Agree
Unavailability of Science materials.	2.49 ± 0.84	Disagree
Poor quality of science printed-visual materials.	2.23 ± 0.91	Disagree
Delayed delivery of study materials.	2.35 ± 0.87	Disagree

Table 3 Institutional-related Challenges Perceived by Parents

Institutional-Related Challenges	Mean SD	Interpretation
Poor parent-teacher relationship.	2.17 ± 0.98	Disagree
Delay of vital information from the school to the parents.	2.33 ± 0.87	Disagree
Poor communication relationship.	2.32 ± 0.88	Disagree
The school is far from the children's residence.	2.72 ± 0.98	Agree
No module is available.	2.18 ± 0.95	Disagree

Table 4 Academic Performance of the Pupils

Quarter	Mean (SD)	QD
First quarter	83.6(3.6)	Satisfactory
Second quarter	83.1(3.7)	Satisfactory
Average	83.3(3.3)	Satisfactory

Table 5 Challenges met by Parents and the Academic Performance of their Child.

Type of Challenges	r	p-value	Remarks
Individual-Related Challenges	-0.41	0.04	Significant; Moderate relationship
Instructional-Related Challenges	-0.37	0.03	Significant; Moderate relationship
Institutional-Related Challenges	-0.28	0.039	Significant; Moderate relationship

4. Discussion

In Table 1 that individual-related challenges were predominantly rated as “agree”. Indicator 5, “I have poor teaching skills which lead children to further confusion”, got the highest mean (2.83 ± 0.80). It signifies that poor teaching skills of the parents is the greatest challenge commonly encountered by the parents. While indicator 1, “I lack sufficient time to supervise my children’s studies”, got the lowest mean (2.50 ± 0.87).

In Table 2, about the context of instructional-related challenges, it can be gleaned that out of 5 indicators, only indicator 2 is the only indicator that got an equivalent of “Agree” description. This means that parents find it challenging to have science printed material content too lengthy and comprehensive in scope. In addition, indicator 4, “Poor quality of science printed-visual materials,” got the lowest mean (2.23 ± 0.91) which is described as “Disagree.” This implies that the quality of science printed-visual materials is good. Table 3 revealed that only indicator 4, “The school is far from the children’s residence” with a mean of 2.72, acquired an equivalent description of “Agree” out of 5 indicators. Table 4 shows pupils perform satisfactorily in the first and second quarter of the current academic year with average grades of 83.6 and 83.1, respectively. It only showed that the pupil-respondents performed adequately in modular distance learning.

A moderate, negative correlation between individual-related challenges of the parents and the academic performance of their children in school, was observed and statistically significant ($r=0.41$, $p=.04$). This would suggest that as the individual-related challenges encountered by the parent increases, the academic performance of their children tend to decline. There was also significant, moderate, negative correlation between individual-related challenges of the parents and the academic performance of their children in school, ($r=0.37$, $p=.030$). On the other hand, there was a statistically significant relationship between institutional-related challenges of the parents and the academic performance of their children in school, however, weak, and negative ($r=0.28$, $p=.039$) This signifies that the connection of the academic performance of the students to the institutional-related challenges experienced of the parents is insubstantial.

5. Conclusion

An increase in individual-related and instructional-related challenges of parents tends to decrease their child’s performance. Similarly, as institutional-related challenges increase, children’s academic performance decreases. Therefore, the parents should give ample time to read the lesson and be patient to be able to teach their children well.

Compliance with ethical standards

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Conflict of Interest Statement

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in this study.

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